

Cross-Domain Telemetry Architecture: Real-Time Metrics in the Computing Continuum*

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Abstract

The growing importance of cross-domain collaboration to meet high demand and diverse requirements in service deployments has highlighted the need for robust Continuum Computing solutions. This approach seamlessly integrates computing resources across Cloud and Edge Computing, and beyond, to optimize resource usage and service delivery, even for organizations with limited resources. However, retrieving, sharing, and properly managing metrics about resources acquired across the continuum poses significant challenges. In this regard, telemetry, involving the automated collection and transmission of data, can be enhanced to become a pivotal technology for monitoring in distributed computing. This paper presents the design and implementation of a telemetry-based solution for multi-domain and cross-domain environments, applicable to existing distributed continuum frameworks. The solution facilitates the gathering, analysis, storage, and export of telemetry data across the continuum, while also considering security and privacy to ensure that data metrics are only available to service owners, regardless of the deployment location across the continuum. The solution is being integrated within the FLUIDOS framework as the Telemetry Service component. In the near future, it is expected that implementation results will be validated.

1 Introduction

The growing demand for real-time services has driven significant evolution in IT infrastructures. New models are emerging to optimize resource utilization and service delivery efficiency. One such model is distributed computing, which aims to achieve the Computing Continuum by integrating Edge Computing and Cloud Computing. This revolutionary approach allows companies, even those with limited resources and budgets, to continue offering competitive services. However, the multi/cross-domain nature, as well as the heterogeneity of infrastructure and technology [1] makes the efficient management and monitoring of IT resources more critical than ever.

Telemetry, defined as the automated collection and transmission of data from remote or inaccessible points [2], is essential for real-time monitoring and decision making. In distributed environments, manual monitoring is impractical, so automated data collection is crucial. This continuous stream of data from sensors, devices, and applications allows for a better understanding of system health and performance. This comprehensive understanding enables proactive

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and reactive measures, facilitating complex processes like service orchestration and ensuring adherence to Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

This paper presents the design of a telemetry-based solution for multiple/cross domains, applicable to existing distributed frameworks. The telemetry modules and functionality are designed to be easily integrated into any distributed framework. The paper also discusses how the solution can provide detailed information on resource acquisition and utilization patterns. It covers aspects such as data collection, transmission, storage and analysis, emphasizing the importance of one of the key aspects explored in this paper, which is the ability to incorporate external resources into the monitoring ecosystem. Indeed, in a heterogeneous and distributed environment, the ability to extend monitoring beyond internal (intra-domain) resources to include external (inter-domain) assets becomes indispensable.

This solution is developed within the scope of the FLUIDOS project¹. This project uses Kubernetes as the basis for service deployment and resource management within the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. In addition, provide tools such as Ligo² allowing the connection between different clusters while maintaining privacy and security, which is leveraged for secure data transmission between different domains.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews the related work on telemetry-based solution on Computing Continuum. Section 3 introduces the framework chosen to validate our telemetry architecture design, i.e., FLUIDOS. Section 4 describes the design of our telemetry service and shows the data collected in the local node and in the remote node. Section 5 shows the implementation of the work. Finally, Section 6 provides conclusions and our expectations of future steps.

2 Related Work

The increasing complexity and scale of modern networks, especially with the advent of 5G and NFV, have necessitated advanced telemetry solutions. These solutions provide real-time visibility into network and infrastructure performance, which is critical for optimizing resource utilization and ensuring service reliability. Therefore, their adoption in modern networks is increasing, for example, Zhou et al. [3] introduces NetSeer, a framework for telemetry event for flow and packet networks designed for large-scale cloud networks. NetSeer aims to enhance real-time monitoring and proactive decision-making by providing comprehensive insights into network performance anomalies (NPAs) such as packet drops, congestion, and path changes. Using an approach similar where the detection and mitigation of network problem is the premise, Zhu et al. [4] shows Zoonet, a proactive virtual network telemetry for effective network management in large-scale, multi-tenant cloud environments that provides real-time monitoring and data collection capabilities that are essential for identifying and diagnosing network issues proactively. By leveraging telemetry, Zoonet can detect anomalies and performance degradations across both virtual and physical network layers, enabling rapid troubleshooting and minimizing downtime.

In the realm of 5G network Chochliouros et al. [2] presents a 5G network architecture where the authors highlight the importance of telemetry to support the cognitive and dynamic management of the 5G architecture, as it is collected and analysed in real time, improving the management and optimisation of network resources. A similar approach is taken by Cominardi et al. [5] which shows a programmable and scalable telemetry system designed to monitoring

¹<https://www.fluidos.eu/>

²<https://docs.liqo.io>

the 5G networks. By leveraging in-switch processing capabilities and centralized SDN control, allowing accurate and efficient collection of user-defined network statistics. The authors introduce an API based on finite state machines that allows network operators to configure and execute monitoring tasks. Through experimental validation, they show that it significantly improves measurement accuracy compared to traditional controller-based approaches. Based on these network reconfiguration concepts, Jaehoon et al. [6] shows how intent-based networking (IBN) can streamline network operations by automatically translating high-level intentions into network configurations and policies. Telmetrics is essential in this work for IBN systems to continuously monitor the network and ensure that the network state conforms to the intended policies and configurations. In the same field, but with the particularity of using telemetry for orchestration process guidance to dynamically adjust resources, service orchestration, detection for network reconfigurations, alerts for SLA violations, Blanco et al. [7] presents his work where telemetry collects data from the entire 5G infrastructure, for real-time monitoring and early warning. More security oriented, but very similar Jorquera et al. [8] uses the telemetry for real-time monitoring and proactive security management since provides continuous data collection from network communications, which is essential for detecting operational and cybersecurity threats.

Although telemetry is increasingly present in various network architectures, much remains to be done to take full advantage of the benefits that these components can offer. The goal of this paper is to present a functional and flexible architecture for collecting data from a variety of sources, allowing for comprehensive analysis and utilization to improve system performance, management and real-time monitoring across multiple domains, suited for distributed cloud-edge environments. Furthermore, as S. Gamage et al. [9] point out, the vast amount of data that telemetry can collect, from network data to safety-related information, makes machine learning methods ideal tools that can be trained on this data.

3 The FLUIDOS Framework

This section provides an overview of the FLUIDOS framework, which serves as the foundational environment for our proposed telemetry architecture designed to be align with distributed continuum frameworks. FLUIDOS (Flexible, scaLable, secUre, and decentralIseD Operating System) is an ambitious research project dedicated to developing a decentralized operating system. This system aims to unify distributed node resources and capabilities into a seamless, homogenized interface. By leveraging FLUIDOS, users can deploy and manage services effortlessly, ensuring that all specified requirements and constraints are met without needing to understand the specifics of deployment locations or details. This decentralized approach enables the secure deployment of complex services across multiple FLUIDOS nodes owned by different providers. Each node can offer and use resources or services, providing exceptional flexibility, making FLUIDOS an ideal solution for diverse applications and domains.

Some of the characteristics of FLUIDOS that distinguish it from similar projects are (i) **Deployment Transparency:** decisions on where to run services are made dynamically and autonomously based on service requirements and the current state of the infrastructure, (ii) **Communication transparency:** communication between services is managed as if they were in the same virtual space, facilitating interoperability and efficiency and (iii) **Resource availability transparency:** FLUIDOS allows services to access and use distributed resources across a unified virtual space. This means that a service can automatically scale by leveraging available resources across the entire continuum.

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of a FLUIDOS node, providing a visual representation

Figure 1: Node Architecture

of the system’s structure and capabilities.

To support the advanced features and capabilities mentioned above, FLUIDOS aims to maximize the potential of cutting-edge technologies such as kubernetes. In addition, it uses Liqo for enabling dynamic and seamless Kubernetes multicluster topologies that support heterogeneous infrastructures on-premises, in the cloud and at the edge. This technology offers four main capabilities that distinguish it from other tools: peering, offloading, network fabric and storage fabric.

For managing telemetry in FLUIDOS, our solution focuses specifically on the modules highlighted in the figure 1. (i) Local Telemetry Service: This module collects and manages telemetry data. The Telemetry Service provides other components such as the Orchestrator Node, which is the brain of the architecture, with crucial information for making deployment decisions, as well as the reassociation of services due to poor performance of the node or container or even SLA violations, since the Telemetry Service is also in charge of creating alerts to ensure that everything is working as planned. (ii) Remote Telemetry Service: This module is the same as the local one, but with the particularity that those deployments made in other nodes outside the domain for which we have acquired those resources, the Remote Telemetry Service will be in charge of sending those acquired resources and that information about our deployed services to our Telemetry service. (iii) Ratings and metrics: This module serves as the central database where all information about the infrastructure is stored. It is essential for recording performance data, reliability metrics and other essential information about resources and services.

4 Solution Design

The Telemetry Service is pivotal in aggregating comprehensive data from a diverse amount of devices and resources. This includes collecting metrics from IoT devices, robots, power consumption units, services, containers, and Kubernetes nodes. By capturing such a wide spectrum of data, the telemetry service facilitates effective resource management, continuous

monitoring, and system optimization to ensure that local resources and services are used and operated efficiently and that any anomalies can be resolved quickly. Additionally, it enables precise assessment of carbon footprints, contributing to more sustainable operations. The proposed design allows the telemetry service to be completely flexible and configurable without manual intervention. For instance, in a policy-based approach such FLUIDOS framework, policies are resolved by the Orchestrator Node that is the brain of the architecture, and policy models can be extended for providing on-demand telemetry capabilities that would ask to the telemetry service specific configurations such as: create alerts, monitoring specific metric, send metrics among others. The solution design is mainly composed of a telemetry agent, metric providers, the receiver, filtering/transforming module and the exporter.

4.1 Telemetry Agent

To facilitate the integration of the solution within the continuum framework, a telemetry agent has been designed and developed from scratch. This agent enables the specification of requirements derived from telemetry policies for configuring the telemetry pipeline behavior and the necessary metrics. Consequently, it enhances automation and scalability, and streamlines telemetry management.

4.2 Metric Provider

As its name suggests, metric providers are responsible for retrieving metrics from various resources and delivering them to designated receivers. These providers play a critical role in the telemetry pipeline by ensuring that data is accurately collected from diverse sources, such as applications, infrastructure components, or external services.

4.3 Receivers

Receivers are pivotal components that facilitate the initial ingestion of telemetry data into the observability pipeline. They serve as the main entry points for various types of telemetry data, including traces, metrics, and logs, collected by agents deployed across diverse environments, applications, infrastructure, and external services. They can convert incoming telemetry data from its native format into the formats required by the exporters.

4.4 Processing Module

The Processing Module, enables the execution of various operations on the received telemetry data, aligning with telemetry policies and business requirements. Its functionalities are designed to enhance the utility and manageability of the data before it is forwarded to storage or analysis systems. It provides functionalities such as data transformation, filtering, aggregation, enrichment, sampling or normalization.

4.5 Exporter

Exporters consume telemetry data and delivering it to components or applications responsible for monitoring and analysis. These components can include observability platforms, logging systems, and analytics tools. The exporter module is responsible for data consumption, transformation, delivery and integration among others.

Aligned to the high-level design provided by continuum frameworks like FLUIDOS, the solution is mainly based in two different operation modes: Local telemetry and remote telemetry, each tailored to specific requirements and operational contexts.

4.6 Local Telemetry Service

The Local Telemetry Service, as its name indicates, is in charge of collecting all the information from the local node. As illustrated in Figure 2, which presents a high-level design of the system in the FLUIDOS scope, the Local Telemetry Service collects information from a variety of resources within the node. This information encompasses data from hardware components, such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and disk I/O, all collected from the underlying technologies.

Figure 2: Local Telemetry Service

The information collected by the Telemetry Service undergoes a process of storage and processing (transformation and filtering), but as the figure shows the path is totally flexible depending on the telemetry requirements. This is, once the receiver acquires the data (step 1 Figure 2), data could be sent directly to the exporter, without processing (Figure 2 - step 2a). It could be processed and stored, processed and exported (Figure 2 - step 2b), or directly stored and exported (Figure 2 - step 2c). In case we decide to process the data before storing them, the data can undergo different transformations, e.g., additional contextual information can be added to them, such as the domain they belong to. In this case, this transformation ensures that the data is properly categorized, facilitating easier access and more meaningful analysis. It can also be filtered to remove any duplicates, ensuring that only unique and relevant information is retained, filtered based on metric name or attributes, among others. This filtering process

is crucial to maintaining the accuracy and efficiency of the tracking system, as it prevents the database from becoming saturated with redundant entries and reduces the possibility of misleading analysis. Once the data has been processed correctly, it can be stored or sent to the Exporter. The Exporter acts as a centralized endpoint for other components, such as the FLUIDOS Node Orchestrator, that require up-to-date information on the status of the infrastructure as well as data base to store the data. This information will help support decision making and effective resource management. In addition, the Exporter is equipped with alerting capabilities. This functionality allows generating alerts based on predefined criteria. It ensures that any anomalies or performance issues in services, nodes or other monitored elements are quickly identified and resolved. These alerts are essential for maintaining the smooth operation of the Continuum ecosystem, as they allow you to respond quickly to potential problems, minimizing downtime and mitigating risks. As shown, the Telemetry Service is completely flexible and scalable, so we can treat different Receivers differently, going through different steps depending on the requirements or preferences of each node.

4.7 Remote Telemetry Service

Previously, it was stated that FLUIDOS is able to provide Continuum Computing by acquiring resources across the entire Continuum, in a transparent manner for deployments, communication and available resources. Remote telemetry is essential for monitoring and visualizing the status of acquired resources and services deployed on remote nodes, which may be outside our infrastructure and even outside our domain.

Figure 3: Remote Telemetry Service

As shown in the figure 3, the data collection and transformation process is similar in both, local and remote resources. However, now the process has an important particularity: metrics gathered (receiver) in deployments that were delegated from other nodes (remote nodes) must be sent to the data owner. For instance, if the FLUIDOS Node delegated the deployment of a service ‘A’ in the FLUIDOS Remote Node, metrics gathered in the FLUIDOS Remote Node

related to service ‘A’ must be sent to the FLUIDOS Node. Thus, those metrics should not be available as usable data in the FLUIDOS Remote Node scope. This ensures that metrics are only provided to its owners, thus maintaining privacy and information security.

In a similar way to the previous case, and according to the telemetry requirements, data can follow different paths with different aims. Once the data is acquired (Fig. 3 - step 1), it can be sent to the owner in different ways. It could be sent directly, without processing to the owner receiver (Fig. 3 - step 2a) or to the owner exporter Fig. 3 - step 2b). Or it could be processed before sending to the owner receiver Fig. 3 - step 2c) or to the owner exporter Fig. 3 - step 2d). This provide a great versatility and extensibility to cope with different security and privacy scenarios.

To protect the communication between the different Telemetry Services, a secure network channel must be used. In this regard, in FLUIDOS, the network created by Liqo is used, which establishes a secure tunnel between the nodes involved. This tunnel allows the transmission of data to the Exporters in such a way that both privacy and security of the transmitted data is guaranteed. Thanks to this infrastructure, it is possible to maintain a continuous and secure monitoring of all resources and services deployed, regardless of their location or domain of origin. This approach not only ensures transparency and privacy, but also enables efficient and coordinated management of distributed resources. By sending the right metrics to the right targets, responsiveness is optimized and decision making is improved, as each FLUIDOS participant can access accurate and relevant information about the status of its resources and services.

5 Implementation

Figure 4: Implementation Scenario

After outlining the high-level design, we will describe the implementation of the solution, highlighting the challenges we faced during the design versus implementation phase. The imple-

mentation available on GitHub³ has been validated, tested and deployed in FLUIDOS scope. As shown in Figure 4, several well-known technologies have been used for the development of the Telemetry Service, all of which have been deployed in Kubernetes. First, receivers are required. A receiver is a component that defines how and from where the telemetry data is collected. To this aim, we deployed and configured OpenTelemetry Collector (OTEL Collector) which is the central component of the Telemetry Service whose version used is the 0.96. We use OTEL Collector as it is an open-source service within the OpenTelemetry ecosystem that tries to unify the collection, processing and export of data, before sending them to the different backends or databases, providing great freedom and flexibility to deal with these data or metrics. For this purpose, OTEL Collector provides a pipeline where we indicate the receiver, processor and exporter, for each metric we want.

Given that the solution must obtain metrics from various sources, several receivers have been defined. Specifically, receivers for gRPC and HTTP were established to receive custom metrics. A receiver for Prometheus has been also configured to gather metrics from different resources in the format Prometheus requires as exporter. Next, metrics providers are required. In our solution, metrics are provided by Node Exporter and Kube Static Metrics. On the one hand, Node Exporter is an agent deployed in Kubernetes which is inside the Prometheus project and is in charge of gathering hardware and OS metrics from the host machine. On the other hand, Kube Static Metric is another agent deployed on the Kubernetes cluster which belongs to the Kubernetes project itself and aims to generate metrics based on the state of Kubernetes component objects such as pods, nodes and deployments.

The next step is to configure the “processor”, within OTEL Collector. The processing step can be composed of filtering, adding/deleting, renaming, or recalculating. In this work, it has been configured by adding domain and cluster tags to the metrics, as well as other useful attributes such as instance ID and Pod UID. The data are also filtered to avoid duplication from different sources, and the last configuration on this step is the metrics aggregation, which has been configured to group the metrics, sending them in batches of 10,000 with a 5-second timeout.

Finally, the configuration of the “exporter” is required in the OTEL Collector pipeline. For the purpose of this paper, only one exporter has been configured, this exporter is Prometheus in its version 2.50.0. Prometheus is a open-source tool for monitoring and alert creation that has a powerful query language, which in turn acts as a database for storing time series data. In our proposed implementation, each node within the FLUIDOS framework maintains local storage for immediate telemetry data, enabling fast access and low-latency monitoring and privacy data preserving. The architecture is not limited to a centralized storage model; it is flexible enough to support a distributed database approach. Metrics are periodically synchronized with a central storage system that aggregates data from multiple workers. Additionally, we have deployed Alert Manager in its version 0.27 that belongs to Prometheus to be able to push alerts as these when triggered can be configured to notify in different ways.

The implementation mentioned so far is totally aligned with the cycle shown in the figure 2 in the design section. To validate the implementation for the remote telemetry approach, a new OTEL Collector configuration is added in a new pipeline with the metrics to be sent. To this pipeline a new receiver for Prometheus is defined, but this receiver has been configured in such a way that it only takes those metrics of a specific namespace. This namespace appears in the local and remote node and is the one in which the resource sharing (offloading) was done using the Liqo tool. Despite there are different possible paths as stated in the design section, in this implementation we follow the flow that processes data, adding the cluster and domain

³<https://github.com/fluidos-project/telemetry>

tags, and then metrics are directly sent to the Prometheus exporter in the data owner node. By configuring this new pipeline we avoid sending metrics that we are not interested in, as well as we do not provide metrics to undesired targets, gaining in security and privacy. In addition, the communication between local and remote Telemetry Service is achieved thanks to the VPN that Ligo offers between clusters.

Figure 5: CPU metric

Figure 6: Latency metric

The figure 5 illustrates an example of a remote metric. In this scenario, the workload from the FLUIDOS node in the UMU domain has been offloaded to a remote FLUIDOS node in the IBM domain. The remote node then sends metrics back to the local UMU node, specifically related to its container (in this case, an NGINX container) and CPU usage. This data allows for a comprehensive understanding of how well the offloaded tasks are being handled remotely, providing insights into resource utilization. Moreover, Another important metric, shown in Figure 6, is the latency between the nodes. Since the local node may serve as the entry point for the service and forward requests to the remote node, monitoring this latency is crucial for ensuring connectivity.

To ease the integration of the solution in continuum framework, a telemetry agent has been implemented from scratch. It allows providing requirements, derived from telemetry policies for configuring the telemetry pipeline behaviour as well as the required metrics, thus increasing automation and scalability and facilitating telemetry management. The agent implements an HTTP API providing parameters such as the namespace and the exporter address. It manages the configuration of its OTEL Collector, abstracting technical details and avoiding the need to do this process by hand. The parameter exporter address is an internal address of the cluster provide it by CNI plugin of Kubernetes as Ligo make a tunnel connection between the clusters.

6 Conclusions and Future work

This paper presents a telemetry architecture designed for cloud computing and cross-domain environments, advancing the vision of continuum computing. Built on the FLUIDOS framework, it integrates telemetry data from diverse sources and components, utilizing tools like Ligo for secure, dynamic cross-cluster connections (transmission data). The architecture supports flexible data collection, transmission, storage, analysis, and transformation through modular pipelines. Integrating external resource metrics is essential for optimizing resource efficiency in multi-domain environments that rely on real-time data.

Future work will focus on validating adaptive decision making in heterogeneous and distributed environments through orchestration algorithms using metrics provided by the telemetry service. Policy creation for complete telemetry service configuration such as add new sources data, pipelines definitions as well as alert generation to ensure compliance with Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

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